

MATRIX CRACKING AND STIFFNESS REDUCTION IN WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Laminates have been fabricated using two woven fibre cloths with twisted and untwisted tows. Twist within the tows from which the cloth is woven is seen to have an effect on the damage mechanisms. The damage in the laminates containing untwisted fibre bundles is similar to damage in cross-ply laminates. The damage observed in the laminate with twisted tows is more complicated. Accumulating damage in the form of matrix cracking has been quantified as a function of applied load and the effect of the damage on the normalised modulus of the two types of laminate is modelled using shear-lag theory.

INTRODUCTION

There has been an increase in the interest shown in woven fibre reinforced polymeric composites for use in primary load-bearing applications. This is partly due to advantages in their handling and processing which, when compared to traditional non-woven materials, more than outweigh the small penalty incurred in their mechanical properties. The elastic behaviour of woven reinforced materials has been the subject of much work. There are both closed form models [1-3] and finite element models [4, 5] discussed in the literature which can be used to predict the undamaged behaviour of these materials. These models are all based on a unit-cell approach. In order to model the behaviour of woven materials after initial cracking, some of these models have been extended to incorporate a unit-cell with reduced properties (e.g. [6]). However, such analyses are not well advanced.

In the present paper, damage morphologies observed in two transparent woven glass fibre reinforced composite materials will be briefly outlined and the effect of increasing damage densities on their normalised stiffness discussed. A model has been proposed based upon equivalent non-woven cross-ply laminates containing full-width, full-thickness transverse ply cracks. The model is used to predict the reduction in the normalised modulus for both laminates with increasing damage concentrations and these predictions are compared with experimental results.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Two woven eight-harness satin GFRP systems have been used. One of the cloths was woven from untwisted tows and the other comprised tows made from three finer bundles twisted together. Laminates were fabricated using a modified wet lay-up process with two layers of glass cloth and epoxy resin matrix (epoxy Epikote 828, curing agent nadic methyl anhydride (NMA) and accelerator K61B) with a cure cycle of three hours at 100°C and a post cure of three hours at 150°C. The test coupons (20 mm x 125 mm) were cut from the laminates using a water cooled diamond saw. End-tags 20 mm x 20 mm were attached using Permabond F241 adhesive with initiator No.1. Strain gauges were bonded to the centre of one face with cyanoacrylate adhesive.

In order to study the damage morphologies associated with particular stress levels, quasi-static uniaxial tensile loading of individual coupons was conducted to a designated stress. Observations of the resulting damage were made in two orthogonal planes parallel and perpendicular to the applied load. Multiple loading of coupons allowed the effect of incremental damage concentrations on the normalised stiffness of the laminate to be measured.

OBSERVATIONS OF DAMAGE

The damage observed in the laminates with twisted and untwisted tows was very different. In the laminate fabricated using untwisted tows, cracks initiated within the interior of the coupon at a strain of 1.2%. These cracks propagated many millimetres across the width of the coupon and frequently extended from one laminate edge to the other, as shown in figure 1a. Microscopic examinations of these cracks in polished edge sections (figure 1b) showed that the cracks grew through both the impregnated 90° bundles and the resin rich regions. The three "phases" of the composite (0° and 90° impregnated bundles and the resin rich regions) can be seen clearly in such edge sections.

The damage observed in the laminate with a cloth woven from twisted tows was more complicated [7]. Cracks were initiated at strains of approximately 0.6% at the interface between the impregnated 90° bundles and the resin rich region. At strains above 0.7%, the cracks were also observed within the interior of the impregnated bundle and examination of edge-sections of the twisted coupons showed the damage to grow within the impregnated 90° bundles alone. A plan view photomicrograph of a coupon after loading to a strain of

0.9% is shown in figure 2a and it can be seen that the cracks are not aligned perpendicular to the loading direction. The deviation of the propagation path from the perpendicular is approximately 7° . There is a further trend in the spatial arrangement of the cracks in that they form a staircase-type patterns at an angle of approximately 72° from the coupon axis. Microscopic examination of the fabric showed that the twist of the fibres within the bundle caused the fibres to cross the tow axis at an angle of approximately 7° . It was also noted that the repeat pattern of the interlocked regions of the weave corresponds to the staircase crack patterns. It is likely that the three-dimensional stress state at the fabric interlock regions promotes crack initiation.

RESULTS

Mechanical property data derived from the quasi-static tests is shown in Table 1. There is a significant difference in the crack initiation strain for the two materials.

The effect of the cracking damage on the normalised modulus of the two laminates is shown in figures 3 and 4. Both sets of experimental data show a gradual loss of modulus with increasing damage density. It should be noted that the damage density parameters used to quantify the damage on the two graphs have similar units and numerical values; however, the values for the material containing untwisted tows are true experimental observations whereas the values for the twisted tow material are derived from measurements of through thickness crack lengths described in a previous paper [7]. Note that figure 4 in this paper is a corrected version of figure 4 in reference [8].

MODELLING

In order to model the effect of the damage on the normalised stiffness of the laminates, a model developed for cross-ply laminates was used. The equation for parabolic shear-lag analysis proposed by Steif [9] for non-woven cross-ply laminates which expresses the reduction in normalised stiffness (E/E_0) as a function of crack spacing ($2s$) is shown below :

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{E_0}{E_1}\right) \left(\frac{b+d}{b} - \frac{E_1}{E_0}\right) \left(\frac{\tanh(\lambda s)}{(\lambda s)}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where :

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{3 G (b+d) E_0}{d^2 b E_2 E_1} \quad (2)$$

E , E_0 , E_1 and E_2 are the moduli of the damaged laminate, the undamaged laminate, the longitudinal lamina and the transverse lamina respectively. G is the shear modulus of the

transverse lamina in the longitudinal direction, d and b are the thicknesses of the individual transverse and longitudinal laminae respectively and $1/2s$ is the damage density.

When modelling the behaviour of the laminate containing untwisted tows it is necessary to use the idealised laminate configurations shown in figure 5. This is to cover the range of localised small scale laminate lay-ups which are observed in polished edge-sections of woven reinforced materials. The idealised laminates are divided into two sections; an internal sub-laminate, which contains the region in which the cracking occurs and the external plies which play no part in the damage mechanism. Shear-lag theory is applied to the internal sub-laminate alone and the reduction in its stiffness, for a specific damage density, is calculated. The reduced sub-laminate modulus can then be combined with the unchanged external ply modulus, using a rule of mixtures expression, to give the prediction for the laminate normalised modulus corresponding to a specific damage density.

The idealised laminate for the laminate containing twisted tows is shown in figure 6. The fragmented cracks observed in these laminates are contained within the 90° tows and are usually bounded by 0° bundles on one side and a resin rich region on the other. In order to duplicate this, the cracks are assumed to grow within the two remote 90° plies of the unbalanced idealised laminate. Shear-lag theory is applied to the two balanced sub-laminates and the normalised modulus for the idealised laminate as a whole is calculated by combining the two sub-laminate moduli using a rule of mixtures expression.

The values for the different moduli required in the calculations can be obtained from base properties of the glass fibres and the resin in conjunction with the overall glass volume fraction and the area fractions of the three constituents (90° impregnated bundles, 0° impregnated bundles and resin rich region). However, for consistency, the predicted initial (undamaged) laminate moduli, calculated using a rule of mixtures expression, must be equal to the measured experimental values. To achieve this, two predictions have been made. In each case, one of the impregnated bundle stiffnesses (either 0° or 90° tows) is altered such that the calculated value and the experimental value of the undamaged stiffness are equal.

For example, if the modulus of E-glass is taken to be 74 GPa, this is used to calculate the modulus of the impregnated 0° bundles, which is used in conjunction with the experimentally measured laminate moduli and the experimental matrix modulus to calculate a value for the stiffness of the 90° impregnated bundle. The second approach is to calculate a value for the modulus of the impregnated 0° bundles using a value for the 90° impregnated bundle stiffness taken from literature in conjunction with the experimental laminate modulus. The values used for the modelling are shown in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

Graphs 3 and 4 show the experimental data and model predictions for the reduction in the normalised modulus (E/E_0) against damage density ($1/2s$) for the laminates with untwisted and twisted tows. The laminates containing twisted tows show a reduction in the normalised modulus which is significantly less than that shown by the laminate containing untwisted tows. The damage morphologies observed within the material containing twisted tows are

confined to the 90° bundles unlike the laminate with untwisted tows for which the crack extends across the fibre bundles and resin rich regions.

The trends of reduction in normalised moduli of both materials are predicted by the models presented above. The data for the laminates with untwisted tows lie above the model. This is because all cracks in the idealised laminates are assumed to grow through the full thickness of 90° plies, which does not happen in practice. The data tend to fall below the model curves for the laminates with twisted tows. This is due to the models not accommodating the situation in which two cracked transverse tows are adjacent. Further work is in hand to characterise the damage more fully so that the models may be improved.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of twist within the bundles of woven fibre reinforced epoxy laminates has been examined. Two woven glass fabrics were used, one woven from untwisted tows, the other from twisted tows. Observations of the damage morphologies within the two composite systems showed that there are different mechanisms involved in the initiation and propagation of cracks in the different laminates.

The cracks observed in the untwisted laminates were similar to those found in cross-ply materials in that the cracks were generally bounded by 0° fibres. The damage observed in the laminates with twisted tows comprised a sea of smaller cracks confined within the 90° impregnated bundles. Preliminary shear-lag models enable trends in the reduction of normalised modulus with crack density to be predicted.

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REFERENCES

1. Chou T.W. and Ishikawa T.
Chapter 7: Textile Structural Composites, vol 3 (1989) 209-265.
Elsevier, editors Chou T. W. and Ko F.K.
2. Naik N.K. and Shembekar P.S.
J. Comp. Mat. vol 26 (1992) no 15, 2196-2225.
3. Shembekar P.S. and Naik N.K.
J. Comp. Mat. vol 26 (1992) no 15, 2226-2246.

4. Zhang Y. and Dai Y.
Computers and Structures vol **36** (1993) no.5, 839-844.
5. Dasgupta A. and Bhandarkar S.M.
Transactions ASME. J. Eng. Mat. vol **116** (1994) no 1, 99-105.
6. Kriz R.D. and Muster W.J.
NBSIR-85/3025 Tech Report (1985).
Nat. Bureau of Sids. Fracture & Deformation.
7. Marsden W. M., Boniface L., Ogin S.L. and Smith P.A.
Proc. Fibre Reinforced Composites, Newcastle upon Tyne (1994), 31/1-31/9.
8. Boniface L., Gao F., Marsden W.M., Ogin S.L. and Smith P.A.
Proc. Deformation and Fracture of Composites, University of Surrey (1995) 317-325.
9. Steif P.S., Appendix to Ogin S. L., Smith P. A. and Beaumont P. W. R.
Technical Report (1984) CUED/C/MATS/TR105
Cambridge University Engineering Dept.

TABLES

TABLE 1. Mechanical properties of woven laminates.

Property	Untwisted tow laminates	Twisted tow laminates
E_{Lam}	19.6 ± 0.3 GPa	19.2 ± 0.5 GPa
$\epsilon_{initiation}$	1.2 %	0.6 %
$\epsilon_{failure}$	1.8 %	2.2 %

TABLE 2. Properties of the individual plies in the idealised laminates used for modelling.

Lam V_f glass	Untwisted tow laminates				Twisted tow laminates			
	0.36				0.37			
Bundle prop	V_f glass	V_f bundle	E_{0° fixed	E_{90° fixed	V_f glass	V_f bundle	E_{0° fixed	E_{90° fixed
0° bundle	0.60	0.32	45.8	47.7	0.58	0.32	44.1	43.0
90° bundle	0.60	0.32	14.8	13.0	0.58	0.32	11.9	13.0

Figure 1. (a) Plan view and (b) edge section of the damage observed in the laminates containing untwisted tows.

Figure 2. (a) Plan view and (b) edge section of the damage observed in the laminates containing twisted tows.

Figure 3. Graph showing experimental data and model predictions for the reduction in normalised modulus against crack density for laminates containing untwisted tows.

Figure 4. Graph showing experimental data and model predictions for the reduction in normalised modulus against crack density for laminates containing twisted tows.

Figure 5. Schematic of the two idealised laminate lay-ups used for the modelling of the behaviour of the laminate containing untwisted tows.

Figure 6. Schematic of the unbalanced laminate lay-up used for the modelling of the behaviour of the laminate containing twisted tows.